

Experiments on technology-assisted free improvisational practices with an ensemble of saxophone

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Abstract: *Free Improvisation (FI) has been increasingly used as a tool for musical education because it provides an exploratory environment that facilitates learning motor skills, appreciating sonorities, and interacting with others. In this work, we take a step further in this paradigm by using Ubiquitous Computing (UC) technology to facilitate FI by providing active feedback to the musicians about their performance. We call this approach TAFI (Technology-Assisted Free Improvisation). Experiments in FI sessions with a saxophone ensemble indicate that TAFI fostered creativity and participation both in in-person and in remote (network-connected) FI sessions.*

1. Introduction

Free Improvisation (FI) is a musical practice that emerged in Europe as part of an artistic movement especially strong in Britain, during the 1970s [Canonne, 2016]. Some researchers such as Canonne (2016), Costa (2015) and Falleiros (2012) support the idea that FI comes from a merge of European contemporary formal music and North American Free Jazz. Since then FI has established itself in our culture, for some even as a contemporary way of life, in consonance with our social behavior and individual state of mind¹.

FI is not a "style" or compositional trend. Instead, FI aims to be an experimental, empirical and generally collective musical practice that avoids submitting or become subordinate to any specific aesthetic musical tendency, even if it inevitably converges and dialogues with many of the contemporary musical practices and genres. One important aspect to understand FI is that it is not a geographically constricted manifestation. There are FI musicians spread all over the world. Together they compound a diversified and active worldwide FI panorama [Clemente et al, 2019]

¹ Although FI is a term that tights together the common practice of many improvisers, it is also a term that has currently been criticized precisely for its broad range of meanings. As such, other terms more specific have been gradually more frequently used, such as "Transstilistic", by Sarath (2010), "Hyperimprovisation", by Falleiros (2013) and "Generative improvisation", by Savouret (2010).

Two features that are important for any musician to pay attention while being part of a FI session are Listening and Performing. Together, they draw the musician into a type of "readiness state". This is achieved by attentively listening to all improvisers while keeping a conscious action of performing, in order to accurately play their "sound image" (the set of all musical possibilities that each musician has, even before start playing). In this situation, there is no difference between thinking and playing [Falleiros, 2012]. In this type of musical manifestation, the FI performance advances based on the compromise of what can and what cannot be done by each musician. This happens through a continuous decision-making process, in which each musician attempts to explore their own instrument's methods and sounds thus acquiring new musical methods and possibilities of sonorities based on what they intuitively learned. An FI session can resemble a type of soundscape, that is, a landscape of possible musical organized sounds, because its sonority is ecologically composed by the whole performing group. This soundscape emerges from an evolving musical prosody, which is simultaneously self-similar and novelty-seeking. This creation is collaborative, distributed and therefore utmosly anonymous [Falleiros 2012, p.16-30].

The interpretive activity of FI comes from its typically spontaneous execution, in which the musical material is exposed in collaboratively, leading to an aesthetics that explores different motivational forms new improvisation results. This makes FI a potential educational tool that may allow the foraging of musical cooperation and space sharing among students of music, which in turn fits into the interests of music education. These educational strategies are applied within musical groups such as the one presented by Edward Sarath, which teaches traditional music theory through the use of improvisation [Sarath, 2010]. The use of FI practice for musical education can come along with suggestions for musical exercises addressed by all in the group performing the FI session, as the ones presented in this paper, which are done with a saxophone ensemble of music students. In order to make it possible, we used three important guidelines to the FI performance [Matthews, 2012: 22-26]: 1) The creative process is more important than the musical outcome. 2) All participants must interact with the whole group so to promote the development of a collective musical identity. 3) Sound is the media that allows the entire creative process.

Based on these principles, we performed 4 experiments with FI. The first one is a baseline conventional FI session, without any resource of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). This was done in order to compare its results with the other 3 experiments, that use ICT. The second experiment is a FI session uses a video game as ICT resource. This experiment derived from a previous research² that used a commercial video-game, developed by Atari Company, called "Adventure"³. The third experiment is a FI with UC (Ubiquitous Computing). This one uses a free app, called MobMuPlat⁴ that allows to run a real time computer model programmed in Pd (Pure Data⁵) in most types of smartphones (Android or iOS). This patch (as a computer model is called in Pd) was specially designed for this experiment. This one promotes the monitoring of melodic variations in loudness and pitch, performed locally for each musician in the FI group. They were asked to run this patch in his or her own

² CNPq research group: dgp.cnpq.br/dgp/espelhogrupo/5225053539670789.

³ "Adventure" was the game of the year in 1979, for Atari 2600 platform. It is considered to be the first video game of action and adventure.

⁴ MobMuPlat (Mobile Music Platform) <http://danieliglesia.com/mobmuplat/>

⁵ <https://puredata.info>

smartphone while playing in the FI session. The fourth experiment uses the same patch from the experiment 3, but here monitoring the melodic variation of each musician in an FI remotely performed, where each participant is in a different location and all FI group is interacting through an audio conference call, making it a truly acousmatic distributed FI performance. As further detailed, these experiments were organized in such order to describe the technological path from FI without any ICT assistance till a FI deeply dependant of ICT and even UC.

All experiments were applied to a group students of saxophone, from a saxophone ensemble of ELM⁶, at the University of Campinas (UNICAMP). This ensemble currently has up to 16 saxophone players in many levels of expertise (musicians with 2 to 4 years of training). These students already had some basic contact with FI foundations throughout 5 workshops that took place in 2019, where they also answered surveys about their musical experiences and opinions after participating in the FI performances. The questions were about their understanding and impressions after each FI session, such as: How comfortable they felt during improvisation; How pleasant was the group sonority; How much they perceive their musicality improving; How was their perception of group's timing and tuning during improvisation; and so forth. The answers were ranked by each participant in a discrete scale ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 was always related to a pessimist or negative impression (e.g. no results, nothing changed, not interesting, not pleasant, etc), and 5 was related to a very positive or pleasant assessment (e.g. useful, meaningful, important, interesting, educating, intriguing, pleasant, etc.) [Clemente et al, 2020]. This work is part of a doctoral research in which the use of FI is studied as a strategy for music education, specially to improve musicality, here defined as the musician's ability of perceiving, appreciating and making music [Honing, 2018]. Musicality improvement is measured by the observation of his or her active listening, rhythmic synchronization, loudness and pitch perception and domain, as well as the acquisition and control of new technical skills in the musical instrument. In this article we present an extension of it, with the use of technology-assisted FI with UC resources. The goal here is to help FI to expand its use and effects for music education, specially in the development of musicality. This is here called TAFI (Technology-Assisted Free Improvisation), that uses UC resources nowadays easily available through the smartphones that almost everybody nowadays owns. With it we developed a simple computer model to monitor 2 fundamental aspects of FI melodic variation. Many other strategies can and hopefully will be further implemented and tested for this subject. The UC resource for FI are centered in the experiments 3 and 4, where the before mentioned customized Pd patch was developed and used to measure in real time the variation of pitch (notes played) and loudness (their perceived intensity) of each musician's in the FI session.

2. FI as a music education resource for the development of musicality

Musicality is one of those elusive aesthetic terms referring to a musical quality found in a performer or a particular performance that is easy to perceive but hard to define. It is directly related to expressiveness in musical performance, a subject broadly studied by many, such as [Fabian, 2014]. Here we define musicality as the ability of a

⁶ *Escola Livre de Música* is part of CIDDIC (Center for Integration, Documentation and Cultural Diffusion), one of the interdisciplinary centers and nuclei of COCEN (Coordination of Centers and Nuclei) of UNICAMP, the school aims to function as a laboratory for experimental musical pedagogies.

musician to consciously control and deliver an expressive performance. Expressiveness is achieved by the manipulation of microstructural elements (meaning borderline perceptual) of a musical performance, such as subtle variations of timing, loudness and even pitch. In that sense, practices such as FI, that explore intuitive musical interaction can help the development of musicality.

According to Sarath (2010) the set of performance possibilities of each FI instrumentalist weaves the musical creation taking place within the group. In this way, each musician finds new paradigms that lead to the acquisition of methods to explore sonorities by encouraging creativity, thus improving the musician's musicality. Each performer who participates in a FI group starts from interacting with his or her own previous experience. That is to say that FI becomes a learning model through improvisation after stylization, which is given by the musician's background. The contribution of each one comes from personal and musical own experience, developed throughout an entire lifespan, which may have been built in many ways, such as, by what the musician heard before, places lived or visited, predilect (or repulsive) musical genres and styles, relationships, performances through which the one's musical aesthetic was expressed and aimed to be translated into sounds [Sarath 2010, p. 32-53].

Chefa Alonso (2007) lists some principles to follow as pedagogical strategy for music education during FI where emphasis is given to the interpersonal musical relationship based on equality and bound. Simply by how the instrument is explored during a FI session, extended techniques are learned by all group members, such as how to solve everyday performatic problems by activities carried out through and during the FI. Alonso also emphasizes that in many occasions creative or improvisational activities should come along with traditional musical academic curricula. In the context of Latin America, the application of FI as part of pedagogical tools are mostly centered in the figure of a famous brazilian (born in German) teacher, composer and musicologist, Hans-Joachim Koellreutter (1997), who used improvisational practices in his compositional and educational work. According to Brito (2003), improvisational activities proposed by Koellreutter also enhanced aspects of organization, coexistence, collaboration among equals, as well as the contact with contemporary musical practices. Brito points out that improvisation should be understood as an important pedagogical tool that accompanies the entire music educational process by giving to the educators opportunities for observing and analysing what trends and bounds students establish with the sound materials to which they have been exposed and are producing [Bruto 2003, p.152]. Carlos Kater (2017) studies the use of FI practice as a musical teaching tool for sound explorations and experiences where open and spontaneous exposure to musical potentially risky situations are welcome and even encouraged. For Kater, in such musical moments, teachers can progressively contemplate and propose for students recreational activities with greater degree of inaccuracy and indeterminacy, which invite the students to position, interact and take decisions [Kater 2017, p.158]. Rogério Costa (2016, p.84), a well known brazilian author on FI subject, points out that this practice has been seen as a pedagogical strategy that can be used to provide the building of knowledge and skills such as listening and the understanding the fundamental aspects of musical composition as FI sets them into action thought the musician's perception of mind and body integration where sound information flows as dynamic musical events that occur during FI musical practice.

Recent research conducted by Brietzke (2018) sought to investigate the implementation of improvisational game models for the collective musical initiation of

cello students. This study was applied in three different institutions in São Paulo, Brazil, obtaining enticing results through the use of FI. The results revealed that students felt comfortable with FI practices, in addition of having better recognized structures of musical narratives during the activities. There was also greater and better integration between classmates as well as deeper understanding and consequent approximation of student to contemporary musical narratives. The educators involved in this research reported the development of creativity in the students and the improvement of their teaching-learning processes, although they also pointed out the importance of previously contextualize the FI proposals, linking it with the traditional model of teaching music. In a previous research on the first contact of students with FI, carried out in 2019 by one of the authors of this work (to be published in his ongoing doctoral project) the results show that students engaged in FI practices perceived and reported improvements in their musicality. Through answers from a survey filled out by the participants, they mentioned the musical improvements they perceived in themselves and in the whole group after participating of FI sessions. The improvements were specially perceived when they played pieces from the traditional musical repertoire, such as improvements in the group's tuning and timing. They also indicated improvements in both the individual and group sound quality, probably due to the fact that FI made them more attentive, leading to be more sensitive, connected and relying more in the individual and grouping musical convergence.

3. FI with ICT

As far as we know there are few studies that have dealt with or analysed the pedagogic implications of FI practice in formal music training. This is even more conspicuous on the study of FI aided by resources of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). However, in the last 20 years or so, ICT have become more ubiquitous among society, in any field of expertise, including music education. With the commercial use of internet, started in the 1990s, wide spread publication of digital books, use of desktops, laptops, tablets and the most ubiquitous gadget of all, smartphones, pedagogical changes have been occurring both in the way students learn and teachers produce and present their educational material, in which students have become active members of the learning process, many times seeking information online while the teacher presents them, which can also make the education process more flexible and even fun. In order to ICT resources to become truly effective in nurturing and supporting creative improvisational performances they must also become integral parts of the normal, everyday lifestyle of musicians, immersed in the 'cultural ecology' of their habitats, which seems to be the case of smartphones. Cultural ecology is here understood as the dynamics of people's interactions with and within their environments (Dillon, 2008).

Vesisenaho et al (2017) conducted a study done in Finland for the facilitation of creativity in musical improvisations practiced through ICT. This study showed that FI seemed to effectively reduce the underutilized creative resources in schools, universities, workplaces and many other everyday places. This study follows a conceptual framework where musical improvisation seems to be the creative result of certain ecological cultural interactions in learning environments. This study contributed proving that creative improvisation interactions could be facilitated by ICT, where improvisational development ideas were also presented. The purpose of this study was

to review current practices and integrate them into an appropriate conceptual framework outlining a research and development agenda for future innovative work in the FI (Vesisenaho et al, 2017).

There is also framework known as TPACK (Technology, Pedagogy and Content Knowledge), proposed by Shulman (1986). This is an extension of a previous framework, known as PCK (Pedagogical, Content and Knowledge). Shulman pondered on the fields of expertise that the contemporary pedagogical process need to simultaneously address in order to be truly effective. The PCK framework only acknowledges the merge of pedagogy with content (the scientific knowledge of the teacher on the subject being taught). In this sense, content knowledge refers to "what to teach" and pedagogical knowledge refers to "how to teach". This way, the lema: "pedagogical knowledge of the content" expands the original "pedagogical knowledge" on how to teach, while also inferring that the teacher should know more than just the knowledge of his or her area of expertise, for the effective creation of knowledge in the students. TPACK aggregates "technology to the merge of skills that a teacher nowadays needs to possess. It aims to intersect technology, pedagogy and knowledge, thus becoming a practical framework on how to teach what is supposed to be taught. This can be used in creative practices such as FI, by letting students to interact by using current ICT resources of UC, such as the pedagogical use of smartphones running freely available apps, as the one here presented.

4. Experiments with FI performances

Here is described 2 sessions of experiments on FI elaborated with the students at the ELM saxophone ensemble. The first session has 2 experiments and took place in 2019. The first experiment involved only a traditional session of FI without any ICT resource. The second experiment used ICT but no UC resources. The second session occurred in the begin of 2020 and is also comprised of 2 experiments; both using UC. The first one (experiment 3) used UC local and experiment 4, used UC remote, as further explained. Each FI session lasted about 45 minutes. The participants had different levels of instrumental expertise. All of them already had some previous experience with creative pedagogy (a pedagogical envisioning focussed on acquiring knowledge through playful and creative activities) through the use of FI, from previous encounters in a pilot study carried out in 2019. All experiments were applied in the facilities of ELM / CIDDIC / UNICAMP.

The first experiment was called "Takete-Maluma". It was initially developed by one the author of this paper, Manuel Falleiros, for a graduate-level course in music, based on the improvised musical "signatures" system presented by Alexandros Markeas⁷. This was an activity without any type of ICT. Here, the emphasis was on the musical expressivity where the group of students, all used to play only by interpreting a graphical score, was asked to interpret the figures. This activity aimed to explore the symbolism, as referred in a research carried out by Wolfgang Kohler⁸, known as the "bouba/kiki effect", was adapted for this context by Manuel Falleiros that promotes a free mapping between sounds and graphic shapes. In this experiment two figures were

⁷ Professor of generative improvisation (to know more: <https://revues.mshparisnord.fr/filigrane/index.php?id=395>) at the Paris Conservatoire (CNSMD). http://www.alexandros-markeas.net/html_fr/improvisations/classe-improvisation-generative.php

⁸ Available at: <<https://www.bbc.com/portuguese/geral-39685606>>. Access: Nov. 22 of 2019.

presented, one very pointy and another fairly rounded. The participants were asked to name these two figures. They were asked to freely interpret both figures by referring to them either by “takete” (most linked its name to the pointy one) or “maluma” (mostly linked this name to the rounded one). The students were then asked to create a collective sound texture that best represented the qualities of each figure. Next, a challenge was proposed. Two contrasting sound textures were presented and the students were asked to play their instruments, starting from one and slowly transforming it into something similar to the other one, removing distinctive sound qualities from the previous one and emphasizing the qualities of the next. Usually the resulting sound texture for takete is composed of distant intervals rhythmically separated and with short articulations. For "maluma", the sound texture is normally composed of a smaller scope of acoustic tensions profused of long, well-connected notes.

The second experiment was based on a performance called "Game-Game" developed and released in 2015 by the research group "Contemporary Improvisation, Creative Processes and Musical Cognition" at Unicamp. This performance used the video game "Adventure" as a substitute for a score, exploring the limits of musical writing. In this performance, the participants received a sheet with a two-column table, in the first column are figures with the characters of the game, and the second column, empty, must be filled with musical parameters (for example, scales, long notes, low notes, frullato etc.).

Each one of these parameters was then related with a character of the video game (chosen by the FI group before each performance and changed for each presentation). As part of the performance, it was mandatory that, at the end of it, each musician tear down its own music score in front of the audience, as a form of making it ephemeral and also protesting against the limits imposed by the traditional music notation. Each time a video game character appeared in the screen, a particular musical parameter attributed to it should be performed by each musician in the FI group. The screen was divided into 4 equal parts (quadrants), each one also indicating an specific musical parameter. The position of the characters in the screen also indicated the selection of a quadrant and consequently the playing of its corresponding parameter. Since each character also had attributed a specific musical parameter, both had to be performed together (character and quadrant). Practice proved that this arrangement made this sort of FI game both highly challenging and enjoyable for the performers, as unexpected and even contradictory combinations wouldn't eventually happen during performance. In a pedagogical adaptation of this game, the goal was that the person in control of the game (and for this reason wouldn't be playing together with the rest of the FI group) would be unaware of the musical parameters chosen by the group. Before each FI game, this person would be asked to momentarily leave the room while the group decided which musical parameters would be related to the characters and quadrants. The goal assigned to this person was to discover, while listening to the FI, as many related parameters as possible, before the game ended. This procedure can also be applied in musical classrooms with larger number of students, by divided it into 2 groups, one that plays and another that seeks the parameters. The experiment carried out with the saxophone orchestra aimed to bring an innovative educational proposal that combined musical performance with visual interaction and audacity education. Despite it was created as a purely performing proposal, this activity proved to be a meaningful and useful pedagogical tool for musical perception and creative development.

The third experiment used a simple computer model programmed in Pd (Pure Data); a patch specially developed for this paper, that runs in smartphones as an app. This one is here called TAFI (Technology-Assisted Free Improvisation) and run in most smartphones (Android or iOS) inside a free app MobMuPlat. TAFI collects audio from the smartphone's microphone and measures in real time the dynamic variation of loudness and pitch. Each participant of the FI group where TAFI was tested was asked to download the app and run the referred patch in his or her own smartphone, during the FI session. This turns each smartphone into a real time measurement tool of the variation of each melodic improvisational line from each musician, by measuring its melodic line. The fourth experiment also used TAFI but in a remote fashion. Instead of having the whole FI group gathered together in the same room, this experiment had each participant remotely displaced, away from each other. The musical interaction between them was mediated by a freely available ICT resource that enables audio conference calls (in this experiment we used Skype). Audio only conference call between participants was mandatory in order to make sure that the FI interaction would occur only by means of sound, thus promoting a truly acousmatic experience (without any visual reference from others during the FI group). Each musician was asked to be in a place with good internet reception (to guarantee a fair quality for the network) and preferably in a soundproofed place where he or she wouldn't be disturbed during the FI (such as alone inside of a car). In order to hear the sound of others while playing together through the network, each musician was asked to play wearing headphones. TAFI was also used here to measure in real time the dynamic variations in loudness and pitch of each musician's improvisation. The aesthetical results were provided by the participants of this remote FI group, through an open discussion on their impressions and contrasts about the effects and potentials of local versus remote approach. The idea behind the use of this measurement of melodic variation is to help each musician to have a better and deeper understanding of the musical quality of their improvisations through an impersonal and dynamic feedback given by an algorithm. For now, this patch only measures the dynamic variation of loudness and pitch, however there are a myriad of possibilities to be measured and tested, which can and hopefully will be developed in more complex measurements, in further experiments, as discussed later. The next section describes the development and usage of TAFI.

5. A patch for the dynamic measurement of melodic variance

PureData (Pd) is a visual computer language created by Miller Puckette in the 1990s, developed to allow the creation of dynamic real time computer models (called "patches") for the analysis, processing and synthesis of data, such as control (e.g. MIDI) and audio. Each patch is dynamically interpreted and run continuously, even while the patch is being built or modified (also allowing its use in live coding performances). Pd was specially designed for computer music applications and sound art performances. As mentioned before, recently, the free app MobMuPlat provided a simple yet powerful framework that allows Pd patches to run inside a smartphone and to have access to many of its embedded sensors (e.g. cameras, microphone, GPS, gyroscope, accelerometers, etc.). This opens up the possibilities offered by Pd to explore capabilities in a ubiquitous computing fashion through smartphones. TAFI is a simple patch that aims to help the development of FI for music education by means of UC. The figure below shows its GUI.

Figure 1. TAFI⁹ (technology-assisted free improvisation) Pd (Pure Data) patch frontend GUI (graphical user interface), as seen in the smartphone screen, via MobMuPlat (Mobile Music Platform).

At its top left there is a toggle button labeled "GO" that starts the patch monitoring process. Below that, there is a white slider that allows the user to dynamically control the microphone's smartphone gain. The player has to set its level before starting the monitoring process, leaving it just above the threshold to capture the sound of his or her musical instrument without capturing the sound of others. As the gain slider is adjusted by the player, in its right side there is a black slider that shows the actual sound intensity captured by the microphone. This level is divided in 3 colors: green for low level, yellow for middle level and red for high level. Notes will be detected by the patch only within yellow and red levels, where red level will also capture notes from other musicians (so each musician is required to tackle the gain to keep its level in the yellow range). When a note is captured, the green bang button under the black level slider will switch colors, from green to yellow. This means that notes are being captured and analysed by the patch, in terms of pitch variance, (whose cumulative histogram is depicted in the yellow vertical slider, at right) and loudness variance (whose cumulative histogram is depicted in the orange vertical slider, at far right).

If few (or even one single note) is being played but in different loudness, the vertical yellow column indicator will slowly go upwards. If many different notes are played but with similar loudness, the vertical orange column will slowly raise. Once its maximum value is reached, the orange dots on the top of these two vertical sliders will turn into the word "FIM" meaning that the analysis process is over and the musician should stop playing. The idea here is that the player whose improvisation vary the most finishes the FI session first, till having only one last musician improvising (the one that varied its improvisation the least). The horizontal yellow and orange sliders at the bottom allow the player to set the sensibility of each corresponding melodic parameter. The default value is 3, but it can go from 1 to 9. Above the default level, the cumulative variance pace (shown by the vertical sliders) is faster, and vice versa. This was done for several reasons. Initially because sounds generated by saxophones tend to present less attack than percussive tonal instruments, such as the guitar or the piano (where the patch

⁹ link for download

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1qES65pxyMg_LXLUUDwgkp0DzwbY7NrDZ?usp=sharing

was initially developed and tested). This makes the cumulative loudness variance for saxophone to be slower than the one for piano, turning the whole improvisation session analysis session slower in sax (when using the default setting value). Besides that, varying these sensibilities can let the FI group focussing in different musical nuances. It can change the FI session duration, or make the musician to focus more in one of these melodic aspects. Under these horizontal sliders the white number box shows the overall cumulative melodic variance (given by the product of loudness and pitch variances). Its value ranges from 0 to 1 million. Finally, at the bottom of the screen, there is a small horizontal radio button that shows the pitch of the notes being captured, in letter notation. Below that there is a tiny horizontal slider showing the dynamic fine tuning of each detected note (where the middle range of this slider represents the correct tuning, at the standard A = 440 Hz).

As said before, this is a simple patch whose development aims to state the principle and to demonstrate the possibilities of using UC resources provided by smartphones in creating and using dynamic computer models for the improvement of musicality through the educational use of FI. TAFI was used in the 2 experiments of the second session, as previously mentioned, respectively for local and remote FI. The results of both experiments are described, compared and discussed in the next section.

6. Discussion and conclusion

As seen, this article presented 4 experiments with FI for the development of musicality in students of music. They were organized in a timeline that followed the increase of ICT resources used in each experiment. The first one had as FI resource static images of different graphic shapes. The students were asked to translate these shapes into sounds were they freely associated each one of them with melodic phrases. It was observed there how consensual is the translation of shapes into melodies among students. This experiment showed the synesthetic relation between image and sound which is produced by the mind and constantly used in arts. The second experiment went one step further, using as FI resource animated images. A video game was then introduced. This simple ICT was used as a general and local media for the students to explore simultaneous musical interactions with the game characters and their locations in the screen. Here the FI group was divided in two subgroups, one that transmits (play) and another that receives (listen). The first subgroup had previously arranged, in secrecy, specific musical patterns for each game character and position. The second subgroup had then to listen to the improvisation of the player subgroup while the game was running and, without knowing the improvisational rules previously arranged, had to decode the message, which means, to find out the improvisational rules arranged by the players just by listening to the performance. This explores the concept of information flow explicit category, where music is the media that information is communicated and eventually decoded, even without having semantic content. Here it's also seen how a distributed compositional process such as FI departs from an "storytelling" aesthetic communication style and approaches a "gamification" one, given by the distributed and cooperative flow of creativity and culture. The next experiment show this tendency even stronger. In the third experiment, the app here introduced by the acronym TAFI was distributed for all students, to be played in their own smartphones while they were participating in the FI session. As said before, TAFI measures melodic variation in real time. When started, the variation is accumulated until it reaches a maximum where the

process stops. In this scenario the students naturally treated the FI session as a game¹⁰. Most of the musicians seem to have enjoyed this experience. Some of them offered suggestions for improvements such as using other improvisational rules like measuring the proximity of the notes with a tonal center, or wearing microphones connected to the smartphone and placing it inside the saxophones so the audio leaking would be minimized. However, all students said that had forgotten about the music interaction and focussed only on "winning the game" which meant to finish the process first by varying the melody the most. This can be musically beneficial as it invites each student to try out new melodies, which would mean to generate more variation, however this also dampens musical interaction and replaces it with a form of musical competition. For that reason a simple change in a newer version of TAFI can solve this situation, just by not stopping the cumulative process when a maximum is reached. The fourth experiment also used TAFI but in a remote way. For that, each student was in a different location and all played together through audio conferencing software¹¹. For reasons that seem to be related to information security, these type of apps do not let to record audio while they are in use. For this reason each musician had to use its own smartphone to run TAFI and another computer (or other small device) to run the audio conferencing software (which in theory shouldn't be necessary). This remote interaction lessened a few notches the open competition flourished in the third experiment and promoted more interaction through music once that sound was the only mean of communication to create the informational flow of the remote FI. The opinions here were divided. Some prefer the local FI sessions as this type offers a multimodal experience where humans senses other than hearing are in action and interaction. Few prefer or seem to see a point in having remote interactions as they tunnel the information flow through only one channel (the hearing), which in theory could with continuous practice, eventually make this mind processing enhanced and thus equipping these musician with a better auditory processing for music. Some participants refer to that as lacking the same liveness of human interaction, as it frequently happen in courses of distance education, It is still too early to settle this matter as new and better experiments should be designed, proposed and further explored.

The first session, having been done more than one year previously to the second session, already showed improvements in the musicality of the participants of these FI sessions. Both individual and group sonority improved, according to the students and the teachers who coordinated the FI sessions. The second session using TAFI is still too recent to have offered a solid feedback on the possibilities of improvement of musicality. They shared the same ludic and intuitive atmosphere of the previous session, where the group enjoyed participating and exploring new musical possibilities. TAFI also offers the possibility for each student to make sound experiments in which the melodic variability is not evaluated by another human being, always prone to judge based on personal values, but by an algorithm devoid of personal judgment and thereby providing an evaluation free from human bias thus allowing unusual melodies to flourish. We hope that further developments on this subject may offer more and better tools to nurture, improve and deliver musicality among musicians by means of FI practice assisted by UC.

¹⁰ A video of this session can be watched in the following link: <https://youtu.be/VUOWfZIQZtl>

¹¹ Skype (www.skype.com)

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